

ONLINE JOB PORTAL SYSTEM

Khin Htet Htet Aung
Student, 5th Year, B.C.Sc.

University of Computer Studies, Hinthada

Supervised By

Daw Khaing Thazin Nwe

Department of Information Technology Supporting and Maintenance

University of Computer Studies, Hinthada

Abstract. The Online Job Portal System is an advanced digital platform designed to simplify the job search and recruitment process for both job seekers and employers. This system efficiently manages job listings, applications, and candidate profiles, providing a seamless experience for all users. It enables job seekers to easily browse and apply for job opportunities, upload their resumes, and receive notifications about relevant job openings. Employers can post job vacancies, review applications, and track the status of their recruitment processes, all from a centralized interface. The system ensures accurate record-keeping and reduces administrative burdens, allowing for a more streamlined hiring process. With its intuitive design and powerful features, the Online Job Portal System enhances the efficiency of job matching, improves user satisfaction, and supports better employment outcomes. This platform is a crucial tool for modernizing recruitment practices and offers a scalable solution suitable for companies of any size and job seekers across various industries.

Keyword: J2EE, HTML, CSS, JavaScript, Bootstrap, Spring Boot

INTRODUCTION

The Online Job Portal System is designed to streamline the job search and recruitment processes for both job seekers and employers. It enables job seekers to easily browse job listings, apply for positions, and receive notifications about opportunities that match their skills. At the same time, employers can efficiently post job vacancies, review applications, and manage their recruitment activities from a centralized platform. By reducing administrative burdens and improving job matching accuracy, the system enhances the overall recruitment experience. It supports better employment outcomes by connecting job seekers with relevant opportunities and providing employers with the tools to hire the right candidates quickly and efficiently [5].

PROBLEM

The Online Job Portal System is a highly efficient platform designed for job seekers and employers, particularly for those who may be navigating the complexities of the job market for the first time or need more guidance. Just as a healthy family life is the foundation of happiness, finding the right job or the right candidate is critical to long-term professional success. This system allows job seekers to easily access accurate information about available job opportunities, while also providing employers with a seamless way to manage recruitment and post vacancies. By addressing common challenges faced in the job search

Accepted Date: 25.10.2024

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and hiring process, this platform helps both parties make informed decisions, leading to successful employment outcomes and reducing the uncertainty that often accompanies job transitions [4].

APPROACH

The Online Job Portal System consists of two main roles: Administrator and User. For users, there are two types—visitors who have not logged in and registered users. Visitors can browse the homepage, read job-related news and announcements, view information about career opportunities, and access the contact page for inquiries. However, to apply for jobs, submit resumes, or leave feedback, users must log in. Registered users who are logged in can manage their profiles, submit feedback about their experience, and track the status of job applications through a personalized dashboard. They can also log out when needed, at which point their session will end.

On the administrator side, the admin must first log in to access the system. Once logged in, the admin has full control over managing user accounts, including viewing job seekers' profiles, reviewing feedback, and overseeing job applications. The admin can also upload, update, and delete job-related news and announcements to ensure the system remains current. Additionally, the administrator is responsible for managing job listings and overseeing recruitment processes, which include reviewing applications submitted by job seekers. The system's robust admin functionalities ensure smooth operations and an organized approach to managing the portal's content and user activities.

Figure 1: System Flow Diagram

Figure 2: Database Design

The figure 2 is an Entity-Relationship Diagram (ERD) for a job application system, depicting the relationships between different entities. The user entity stores details like user ID, name, email, and resume, with a primary key (PK) on user-id. The job entity, identified by job-id as the PK, includes job-specific details such as category, description, requirements, and is linked to a company via company-id (a foreign key, FK). The applicant's entity records applications, with application-id as the PK and FKs linking to job-id and user-id, representing the many-to-many relationship between users and jobs. The company entity contains details like company-id, name, and email, with company-id as the PK. The diagram shows how users apply for jobs posted by companies, and how these relationships are structured within the database [3].

RESULTS

The design of each page in the Online Job Portal System has been thoughtfully crafted to be user-friendly and straightforward. Users (visitors) can easily browse job listings, access career resources, view announcements from employers, and find contact information for hiring managers, all without the need to log in—just by using their mobile phones or other devices with internet access. Once logged in, users can view and update their profiles, schedule job interviews, and provide feedback on their experiences to help improve the system. While internet access is necessary to fully utilize the portal, we aim to enhance accessibility in the future to ensure that even users in areas with limited connectivity can benefit from the system. This platform allows job seekers to engage with employers online, reducing the need for in-person visits and ensuring that they receive the latest job information conveniently and efficiently.

Figure 3: Implementation of this system

CONCLUSION

The Online Job Portal System is an essential tool for modernizing recruitment processes and improving employment outcomes for both job seekers and employers. By providing easy access to job listings, career resources, and streamlined communication between candidates and employers, the system plays a pivotal role in connecting qualified individuals with the right opportunities. Its user-friendly design, combined with features such as profile management, appointment scheduling for interviews, and feedback submission, ensures a smooth and efficient job search experience. Ultimately, the system contributes to a more dynamic and accessible job market, supporting the professional growth of individuals and the hiring needs of companies across various industries.

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